

Research Paper

Effects of the parents as teachers home visiting program on children's adjustment at primary school entry: Evidence from the Swiss ZEPPELIN project

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ABSTRACT

This longitudinal RCT investigates the impact of the Parents as Teachers (PAT) early home visiting program on the developmental trajectories of children from at-risk families, focusing on their transition from kindergarten to primary school education. The study, conducted as part of the Swiss ZEPPELIN longitudinal project, aims (1) to assess whether PAT directly improves school adjustment, including academic achievement, socio-emotional adjustment, and school well-being; and (2) to examine the developmental pathways linking early childhood cognitive and socio-emotional skills to school adjustment. Families ($N = 248$) were randomized to intervention and control groups, and their children ($N = 261$) were assessed longitudinally at age 3 years, during kindergarten (4–5 years), and in Grade 1 (6–7 years). Results of structural equation modeling showed no direct effects of PAT on school adjustment in Grade 1. However, indirect effects indicated that PAT contributed to improvements in children's early cognitive and, to a lesser extent, socio-emotional skills, which, in turn, supported school adjustment during the transition to school. The findings suggest that the cognitive pathway represents a meaningful mechanism linking early home visiting to later school adjustment.

Early childhood represents a formative period during which experiences within the family environment lay the groundwork for later development and educational success (Liang et al., 2020; Shonkoff & Phillips, 2000). Supportive and stimulating home environments foster children's cognitive and socio-emotional skills, which are essential for school readiness and long-term academic adjustment (Attig et al., 2023). However, families facing psychosocial risks (e.g., low income, parental stress) often encounter barriers that limit their ability to provide consistent developmental support (Wang & Hassairi, 2025). In this context, early home visiting programs have become a key strategy to strengthen the home learning environment and promote more equitable developmental opportunities from birth onward (Filene et al., 2013; Hilário et al., 2022). This research explores whether participation in the Parents as Teachers (PAT) home visiting program during the first three

years of life predicts children's adjustment from kindergarten to Grade 1 within the Swiss ZEPPELIN (i.e., Zurich Equity Prevention Project with Parents Participation and Integration) randomized trial.

Home visiting programs provide structured, preventive support to caregivers during the first years of their child's life, a period that is especially critical for shaping long-term cognitive and socio-emotional trajectories (Zhang et al., 2023). Delivered through regular home visits, these programs aim to increase parental knowledge, encourage positive parent-child interaction, and link families to community resources (Filene et al., 2013). Prominent home-visiting programs are the Nurse-Family Partnership (NFP), and the Irish Preparing for Life (PFL). The NFP was evaluated in U.S. trials (e.g., Kitzman et al., 2010), and outside the U.S. in Germany (Kliem & Sandner, 2021), Australia (Price et al. 2023), and the United Kingdom (Robling et al., 2021). The PFL was

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evaluated in Ireland (Doyle & the Preparing for Life Evaluation Team, 2019). Meta-analyses on home visiting programs and their outcomes suggest modest but consistent benefits for children's cognitive and/or socio-emotional development (Casillas et al., 2016; Cibralic et al., 2025; Filene et al., 2013). Nevertheless, most studies focus on short-term outcomes, and few have examined whether early gains persist into the transition from kindergarten to primary school. In addition, most home visiting programs were developed and evaluated in the U.S., with only very few programs conducted in other English-speaking countries (e.g. Australia, Price et al. 2023) or non-English-speaking contexts (e.g. Germany, Kliem & Sadler., 2021)

Parents as Teachers (PAT)

PAT is one of the most established home visiting models and one of the few implemented in non-English speaking countries. Developed in the U.S. in the 1980s, PAT is a universal, curriculum-driven home visiting program that supports caregivers during the first three years of the child's life (LeCroy et al., 2024). Core goals include enhancing parental knowledge, improving parenting practices, promoting early detection of developmental delays, and supporting school readiness (Lahti et al., 2019). Trained parent educators deliver the program through individualized home visits, developmental screenings, and group meetings.

The PAT curriculum is grounded in developmental and ecological theories, highlighting the interaction between the child and their proximal environment as central to learning and adjustment (Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 2006). Activities encourage parents to engage in age-appropriate and responsive interactions with their children, providing a stimulating home environment and addressing family well-being (Parents as Teachers National Center, 2011)

U.S. quasi-experimental trials have shown small but significant benefits of PAT on child developmental outcomes and school readiness (Neuhauser, 2014). More recent experimental evidence indicates improvements in cognitive and socio-emotional skills at kindergarten entry (Pais & Sexer, 2023). A large, matched comparison group study further found that former PAT participants in grades 3 to 12 achieved higher standardized academic scores and fewer school related difficulties (Lahti et al., 2019). Together, these studies provide evidence for both short-term and longer-term benefits of PAT, yet little is known about whether early gains translate into successful adjustment during the transition to primary school.

The Swiss PAT project

PAT was adapted for German-speaking contexts and implemented in Switzerland in 2011 as a preventive intervention for families with elevated psychosocial risk (Neuhauser et al., 2015). Unlike the universal orientation of the original U.S. model, the Swiss version employs a risk-targeted recruitment strategy. The ZEPPELIN randomized controlled trial (RCT) follows families from infancy through secondary school. Earlier findings demonstrated that PAT improved primary language skills and reduced problem behavior in high-risk families at age 3 (Schaub et al., 2019), with follow-up effects on German language skills and oppositional behavior in kindergarten (Schaub et al., 2021). Whether these early advantages predict later school adjustment remains unknown.

School adjustment during the transitions to primary education

The transition to primary education marks a significant developmental milestone that requires children to adapt to new academic, social, and behavioral demands (Griebel & Niesel, 2009). How successfully children navigate this transition is consequential, as early school adjustment has been shown to predict later academic engagement and achievement trajectories (Duncan et al., 2007). The Ecological and

Dynamic Model of Transition (Rimm-Kaufman & Pianta, 2000) conceptualizes school entry as a dynamic process shaped by evolving interactions among children, families, classrooms and schools. From this perspective, skills developed prior to school entry are brought into a new relational and institutional context, where their impact depends on how children and their families engage with teachers, peers, and classroom demands over time. These skills are rooted in early interactions within the family environment. From a bioecological perspective (Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 2006), development emerges from ongoing interactions between the child and their proximal environments, particularly the family. Supportive and stimulating home environments foster cognitive skills and socio-emotional skills (Gard et al., 2020; Forget-Dubois et al., 2009; Wang & Hassairi, 2025). These skills contribute to school readiness, early academic success, and school-related well-being (Attig et al., 2023; Fuhrmann et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2023).

In families facing psychosocial risk, cumulative stressors such as low socio-economic background, parental mental illness, or marital conflict may constrain cognitive and emotional enrichment (Gard et al., 2020; Gonzalez et al., 2020). Reduced verbal input and fewer literacy-enriching activities may limit developmental resources and increase vulnerability during the transition to primary school (Mistry et al., 2008; Zauche et al., 2017).

Successful adaptation during the school transition is reflected in *school adjustment*, a multidimensional construct encompassing academic achievement, socio-emotional adjustment, and school well-being (Demirtaş-Zorbaz & Ergene, 2019). Academic achievement reflects how children adapt to formal instruction and acquire foundational skills in reading and mathematics (Duncan et al., 2007). Socio-emotional adjustment refers to children's ability to regulate behavior and form positive peer relationships (Rimm-Kaufman & Pianta, 2000). School well-being reflects children's emotional, social, and academic inclusion within the school environment (Grüter et al., 2023).

Given this multidimensional understanding of school adjustment, an important question is how early interventions may contribute to children's successful adaptation across these domains. Building on evidence from classic early education interventions (Campbell et al., 1998; Reynolds & Ou, 2011; Schweinhart et al., 1993), Ou (2005) identified three mechanisms through which early intervention influences school readiness: (1) enhancing children's cognitive skills, leading to a cognitive advantage and an increased readiness to learn at school entry; (2) fostering socio-emotional skills, resulting in improved socio-emotional adjustment in school; and (3) strengthening parenting practices and providing home enrichment, thus leading to greater family involvement and support for learning. In later childhood, school-related factors and children's commitment to learning tend to become more influential.

Related longitudinal studies have supported the hypotheses on the advantages of promoting children's cognitive skills and family support for home enrichment and parenting practices as benefiting children's school adjustment, but not the hypothesis on fostering children's socio-emotional skills to benefit their school adjustment (Ou, 2005; Reynolds & Ou, 2011).

Together, these perspectives suggest that early interventions may influence later school adjustment through two primary pathways: by strengthening children's cognitive skills and by promoting family sensitive engagement and involvement in children's educational trajectories. In line with the preceding longitudinal findings, effects on socio-emotional outcomes appear less consistently sustained across educational transitions. The present study builds on these theoretical considerations by examining whether PAT participation predicts children's adjustment to primary school across three domains: academic achievement, socio-emotional adjustment, and school well-being.

Current study

The present study extends prior ZEPPELIN findings (Schaub et al.,

2019, 2021) to examine whether early advantages from PAT translate into children's adjustment during the transition to primary school. The study also provides evidence of the effectiveness of home visiting programs beyond English speaking countries.

The study has two main aims: First, to test direct effects of PAT on school adjustment in Grade 1; and second, to examine longitudinal pathways from age three through kindergarten to Grade 1.

Based on prior evidence from PAT evaluations (Lahti et al., 2019; Pais & Sexer, 2023; Schaub et al., 2019; 2021) and the Chicago Longitudinal Study (Ou, 2005), our evaluations of these aims were guided by three hypotheses.

Hypothesis 1: PAT participation positively affects children's school adjustment in Grade 1, reflected in higher academic achievement, better socio-emotional skills, and greater school well-being.

Hypothesis 2: Improved cognitive skills (developmental status, early mathematical and language skills) and socio-emotional skills (reduced problem behavior) facilitate school adjustment.

Hypothesis 3: PAT participation positively influences children's cognitive and socio-emotional skills, which in turn mediate the program's effect on school adjustment in Grade 1.

Method

Study design, participants, and randomization

This study forms part of the Swiss ZEPPELIN longitudinal project. Between 2011 and 2012, families were recruited through various service providers, including parent-child health counseling service and midwives, during or shortly after pregnancy. Eligibility required risk factors in at least two of the following areas: individual (e.g., mental illness), family (e.g., single parent), social (e.g., no social network) or material (e.g., confined living space). These risk factors should not be mitigated by protective factors (e.g. supportive family structures). Children with severe illness or disability were excluded from the study.

Following recruitment, *N* = 255 families were randomized and allocated to the intervention (IG) or the control group (CG) using stratified block randomization (Neuhauser et al., 2015). After allocation, four families declined further participation and three families became ineligible due to child illness, resulting in *N* = 248 families with *N* = 261 children (13 twins). Group allocation was revealed at the baseline visit (t0). After completing the assessment, a sealed, pre-randomized envelope informed families of assignment to the IG (*n* = 132 families, 139 children) or the CG (*n* = 116 families, 122 children). Most children came from families with an immigration background, defined as at least one parent not born in Switzerland (88.7% in the IG, 85.4% in the CG). In addition, families were characterized by relatively low socioeconomic status, and a substantial proportion of mothers had no post-compulsory education, as detailed in Tables 1 and 2.

The study includes repeated assessments from infancy through secondary school. The current investigation uses data from five measurement points: t0, t3, t5, t6 and t7 (Grade 1). These assessment waves correspond to children's developmental stages rather than fixed annual intervals: t0 was conducted in infancy (approximately 3 months), t3 at 3 years, t5 and t6 during kindergarten (approximately ages 4–6 years), and t7 in Grade 1 (approximately 6–7 years). At t0, baseline characteristics were assessed through semi-structured interviews and parent questionnaires. These were conducted during home visits by members of the project team.

Measurement points t1–t3 occurred annually around the children's birthdays. Parent questionnaires were conducted during home visits by members of the project team, whereas development testing was administered at municipal family centers by qualified pediatricians within the study protocol and independent of routine check-ups.

At kindergarten age (t5, t6), individual testing took place in kindergarten by study-trained special education teachers in training. At t7 (Grade 1), class testing took place in classroom group setting and was

Table 1

Baseline Characteristics at t0 by Treatment Group and Grade 1 Participation: Categorical Variables.

Characteristic		IG participation t7		CG participation t7	
		Yes %	No %	Yes %	No %
	Number of Families	<i>n</i> = 80 (60.6)	<i>n</i> = 52 (39.4)	<i>n</i> = 77 (66.4)	<i>n</i> = 39 (33.6)
Child	Girls	53.8	61.5	49.4	46.2
	Preterm	13.8	7.7	11.7	7.7
	First language German	26.3	17.3	19.5	23.1
Mother	First-time mothers	52.5	65.4	56.6	66.7
	Living alone/ single parenthood	11.3	15.7	13.0	18.0
	No post-compulsory education	36.3	42.3	40.3	43.6
	Speaks no German at all	7.5	19.2	9.1	15.4
Family	Hardly speaks any German	18.8	21.2	23.4	7.7
	Communication in German possible	30.0	25.0	23.4	20.5
	Easy communication in German	43.8	34.6	44.2	56.4
	Twins	5.0	5.8	6.5	2.6
	Recruitment with special efforts	11.3*	19.2	22.1*	28.2

Note. χ^2 or Fisher's exact test and two-sided t-test were used. *Differences with *p* < .10 between IG and CG participants at t7. A liberal significance level was used to avoid overlooking potential systematic differences between participants and dropouts.

Table 2

Baseline Characteristics at t0 by Treatment Group and Grade 1 Participation: Continuous Variables.

Characteristic		IG participation t7		CG participation t7	
		Yes <i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	No <i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Yes <i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	No <i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)
Child	Number of siblings	0.6 (0.7)	0.5 (1.0)	0.7 (0.8)	0.6 (1.1)
Family	Socioeconomic status (ISEI)	30.2 ⁺ (23.6)	22.4 (16.1)	36.2 ⁺ (24.3)	22.3 (17.7)
	Psychosocial stress (HBS)	46.9 (16.8)	48.4 (16.3)	43.4 (15.3)	47.7 (15.9)
	Parental self-efficacy	3.7 (0.3)	3.7 (0.3)	3.6 (0.3)	3.7 (0.3)
	Perceived social support	3.1* (0.7)	3.0 (0.9)	3.3* (0.6)	3.1 (0.7)
Mother	Age mother (in years)	30.5 ⁺ (6.0)	27.7 (5.3)	30.7 ⁺ (5.6)	28.4 (5.1)
	Sensitivity (CARE-Index; ≥ 7 adequate to sensitive)	5.5 ⁺ (1.7)	4.9 (1.5)	6.0 (1.8)	5.6 (1.9)

Note. χ^2 or Fisher's exact test and two-sided t-test were used. ⁺Differences with *p* < .10 between participants and dropouts within each treatment group at t7. *Differences with *p* < .10 between IG and CG participants at t7.

supervised by study-trained student assistants (e.g., psychology, special needs education students).

Across all waves, assessors were trained by the research team and followed standardized protocols and manuals to ensure consistent administration. Data collection was conducted using paper-pencil formats at all measurement points; assessments typically lasted 90–120 minutes per family visit at t0–t3, approximately 120 minutes spread over two surveys at t5, approximately 60 minutes at t6, and two surveys of 1 and 2 lessons of 45 and 90 minutes, respectively, at t7.

Participant flow, retention, and selective retention

Fig. S1 (Supplementary Materials) illustrates the progression from the 255 families randomized and allocated to the 248 families available at baseline (t0) and the subsequent follow-up assessments. These 248 families constitute the final randomized sample for all longitudinal analyses.

At program end (t3), 82.6% of families in the IG (109/132) and 87.9% in the CG (102/116) were retained. Retention at t3 was not significantly associated with intervention condition.

At t7, data were collected in three waves (2019–2021) and obtained from 80 families in the IG (60.6% of the original IG sample) and 77 families in the CG (66.4% of the original CG sample), corresponding to 166 children from 117 classes ($M = 1.43$ participating children per class, maximum = 4). Children were on average 6.8 years old ($SD = 0.4$) at school entry, with 58.4 % attending schools with a support program designed for those with a high proportion of pupils from foreign-language, immigrant, and socially disadvantaged families.

Continued participation to t7 was not associated with treatment group, but was related to mothers' age, family socioeconomic status, and maternal sensitivity within the IG (see Tables 1 and 2).

Intervention

The ZEPPELIN study examines the effectiveness of PAT in the German-speaking part of Switzerland. Affiliated providers adhere to model fidelity requirements set by the German umbrella organization and submit annual reports on process quality and program impact.

The PAT program consists of four main components: (1) Bi-weekly to monthly home visits by qualified parent educators over the first three years, focusing on strengthening parents' knowledge and child-sensitive parenting practices, parent-child interactions, and family well-being. (2) Monthly parent group connections that promote parental networking and provide educational information and community services. (3) Annual screenings for child general health and development, including hearing and vision. (4) On-demand support for parents in accessing community resources and public services.

Participants in the IG were visited by one of ten certified PAT trainers, each with additional training in nursing, parental counseling or midwifery. Of the full randomized IG sample ($n = 132$), 77.2% received the recommended minimum of monthly visits over three years. Among IG families who participated through t3 ($n = 113$, including families with no t3 assessment data), the number of home visits ranged from 20 to 71 ($M = 48.07$; ≈ 1.5 visits/month). Families in the CG received no additional support beyond available standard population access to general local municipal services (e.g., breastfeeding counseling, parent counseling).

Measures

The study used a combination of standardized and psychometrically validated developmental and achievement tests, validated parent- and teacher-report instruments for child outcomes, and parent-report questionnaires used as covariates that have been employed in prior research but were not formally validated in all language versions. Performance-based assessments and all teacher reports were administered in German. Parent-report measures were administered in German or in translated form. Written translations were available for the five most common languages represented in the sample. When no written translation was available, questionnaires were translated orally by cultural interpreters.

Family characteristics at baseline (t0)

Family's global risk. Family risk was assessed with the psychometrically validated Heidelberg Stress Scale (HBS; Sidor et al., 2012), based on a semi-structured interview and observational data. The scale

yields a global risk score ranging from 0 (no stress) to 100 (very high stress) across four domains: material, social, family/personal, and child-related stress. In this study, three independent coders conducted the assessments. Inter-rater reliability was moderate to good, with intraclass coefficients (ICC) ranging from 0.64 to 0.84.

Parental self-efficacy. Self-efficacy was assessed using the Self-Efficacy in Infant Care Scale (Prasopkittikun et al., 2006), which was used as a covariate. This 40-item questionnaire covers four domains of caregiving: development, health, safety, and nutrition. Items (e.g., "I can tell what my child likes or dislikes") are rated on a 4-point scale from "I cannot do that at all" to "I can do that very well". Subscales were aggregated to a total mean score with higher values indicating higher self-efficacy. Internal consistency was high (Cronbach $\alpha = 0.86$).

Perceived social support. Perceived social support was assessed as a covariate using a 7-item subscale of the German Parenting Stress Index (Tröster, 2010). Items (e.g., "When I feel down, I always find people who give me confidence.") are rated on a 4-point scale from "Does not apply at all" to "Applies exactly". A mean score was computed with higher scores indicating a higher perceived social support ($\alpha = 0.83$).

Maternal sensitivity. Maternal sensitivity was assessed using the infant CARE-Index (Crittenden, 2010) based on videotaped three-minute parent-child interactions. Scores range from 0 (at-risk) to 14 (sensitive), with values ≥ 7 indicating adequate to sensitive interactional behavior. The CARE-Index is an internationally established observational instrument suitable for intercultural application in early infancy, as verbal language plays a minor role at this age. Three coders were trained and certified by the instrument developer. Inter-rater reliability in the present study was good (ICC = 0.82).

Child outcomes in early childhood (t3) and Kindergarten (t5–t6)

Developmental status at age 3 (t3). Children's primary language, cognitive, and motor development were assessed using the Bayley Scales of Infant Development III (BSID; Reuner & Rosenkranz, 2014), standardized in Germany. The scales yield IQ scores ($M = 100$, $SD = 15$). The BSID-III demonstrates good reliability, with internal consistency for the main scales ranging from $\alpha = 0.86$ to 0.88. Evidence for content and construct validity has been established, and initial support for criterion-related validity is available. Language, cognitive, and motor scores served as indicators for the factor cognitive skills at age 3. The motor subscale was included because it is predictive of later cognitive development (Piek et al., 2008).

Mathematical skills at age 6 (t6). Mathematical skills were assessed using the arithmetical operations subscale of the Swiss WILMA (Kurati Geeler, 2019), which is a short form derived from the German standardized test TEDI-MATH (Kaufmann et al., 2009). The subscale consists of 25 dichotomously coded items assessing additive decomposition, object-based computation, addition, and subtraction. As a derived short form, reliability was estimated in the present sample, showing good reliability ($\alpha = 0.89$).

German language skills at age 6 (t6). German language skills were assessed using the sum score from the *Sprachgewandt* test (Bayer et al., 2013), measuring language comprehension and phonological awareness. Although the instrument was validated in the Canton of Zurich (Switzerland) for kindergarten and Grade 1, the summed score of 45 dichotomously scored items used here was not norm-referenced. Internal consistency in the present sample was good ($\alpha = 0.90$). Mathematical and German language skills formed the factor cognitive skills at t6.

Socio-emotional skills at ages 3 and 5 (t3, t5). Children's socio-emotional skills were assessed using the parent version of the German-standardized Child Behavior Checklist 1½–5 (CBCL 1½–5, Plück et al., 2022), a widely used instrument with established international application (Achenbach & Rescorla, 2000). The CBCL consists of 45 items rated on a 3-point scale from "Not true" to "Exactly or often true". T-scores of DSM-IV-oriented subscales were used and recoded so that higher values mean higher socio-emotional skills. It should be noted that these indicators primarily reflect lower levels of behavioral and

emotional difficulties rather than direct measures of positive socio-emotional skills. To reduce model complexity, selected subscales were combined into broader indicators: Affective/anxiety ($\alpha = 0.83$), attention-deficit, hyperactivity/oppositional defiant ($\alpha = 0.81$), pervasive developmental ($\alpha = 0.76$).

Child outcome measures in Grade 1 (t7)

Academic achievement. Reading skills were assessed using the standardized German WLLP-R (Schneider et al., 2011), which measures decoding speed in the early school years. According to the test manual, the WLLP-R demonstrates high parallel-test reliability ($r = 0.82$ – 0.93) and good retest reliability over a 14-week interval ($r_{tt} = 0.76$ – 0.82). Evidence for construct validity is provided by substantial correlations with other standardized measures of reading performance and with teacher ratings and school grades.

Mathematical skills were assessed using the short version of the standardized *Test zur Erfassung mathematischer Basiskompetenzen ab Schuleintritt* [Basic mathematics skills at school entry] (MBK-1+; Ennemoser et al., 2017), a group-administered test measuring foundational numerical skills relevant for early school mathematics. The short form assesses core arithmetic and number sense skills. The MBK-1+ demonstrates good to excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.83$ – 0.93) and acceptable retest reliability ($r = 0.67$ – 0.77). Predictive validity has been established through substantial correlations with later standardized mathematics achievement tests (e.g., DEMAT 1+, HRT 1–4). T-scores from the WLLP-R and the MBK-1+ were used as indicators for the factor academic achievement.

Socio-emotional skills. Socio-emotional skills were assessed by the parent version of the German Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ-Deu; Klasen et al., 2003), a validated screening instrument. Parents rated 25 items with a 3-point scale from “Not at all true” to “Certainly true”. The four problem subscales (emotional, behavior, hyperactivity, peers) were summed. Scores were recoded so that higher values mean higher socio-emotional skills. Accordingly, higher scores reflect fewer difficulties rather than direct assessment of socio-emotional skills. In the current study, α ranged between 0.57 and 0.67.

School well-being. School wellbeing was assessed with the validated teacher version of the German Perceptions of Inclusion Questionnaire (PIQ, Venetz et al., 2015, 2019). The three subscales emotional inclusion, social inclusion, and academic self-concept were rated on a 3-point scale from “Not at all true” to “Certainly true”. Mean scores were calculated for each subscale and used as indicators of school well-being. Internal consistencies in the present sample ranged from 0.85 to 0.91.

Statistical analyses

The statistical analyses were performed using the statistic software R (R Core Team, 2021). Structural equation models (SEM) were constructed using the packages lavaan 0.6-11 (Rosseel, 2012) and semTools 0.5-6 (Jorgensen et al., 2022). First, Confirmatory Factor Analyses (CFA) were conducted to examine the factor structure of the different constructs. Model fit was assessed using the robust Chi-Square Test of Model Fit (χ^2), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), and the Comparative Fit Index (CFI). Following commonly used guidelines, CFI values of 0.90 or higher were interpreted as indicating acceptable fit and values of 0.95 or higher as good fit, whereas RMSEA values of 0.06 or lower were considered indicative of good model fit (Hu & Bentler, 1999). For identification and scale setting of the latent variable the effect coding method was used (Little et al., 2006). Mean structure was included in the model, allowing for the testing of group differences in latent means. One longitudinal model was built for each outcome of school adjustment to test the hypotheses. Direct intervention effects (Hypothesis 1) on child outcomes in kindergarten and at school age were tested by including a dichotomous grouping variable (1 = IG, 0 = CG) in a longitudinal SEM with covariates (Fig. 1, Models 1a–1c, dashed lines).

Direct longitudinal pathways were tested (Hypothesis 2), by including longitudinal pathways and excluding the effect of treatment group (Fig. 1, models 2a–2c, solid lines). Indirect longitudinal pathway effects (Hypothesis 3) were estimated by extending the former SEM with indirect effects via a dichotomous grouping variable (Fig. 1, models 3a–3c, dotted lines). Maximum Likelihood (ML) with cluster-robust standard errors (Yuan-Bentler scaled test, cluster-robust sandwich estimator) was used as the estimator to account for nested data on the family level due to twins. In this procedure standard errors are weighted according to the clustering. Full Information Maximum Likelihood (FIML) was used across all models to reduce bias from missing data. Auxiliary variables (i.e., sensitivity, recruited with special efforts, mothers' age, number of siblings, socio-economic status, mothers' educational status and children's age at t6) were included in the models for testing the direct intervention effects (Models 1a–1c).

Directed hypotheses were formulated as the promoting approach of the intervention program clearly assumes a positive direction of the effects. Furthermore, it increases the statistical power to detect effects with a smaller sample size (Cohen et al., 2017), which is relevant for this study due to sample attrition. Thus, one-sided p -values were applied for testing the direct intervention effects. For testing the indirect intervention effects, bootstrapped standard errors of means (SE) were applied and one-sided confidence intervals (CI) reported (Bollen & Stine, 1990). Standardized coefficients (β) with standardized standard errors for direct effect models or bootstrapped standard errors for the indirect intervention effects are reported in the results section. Unstandardized coefficients (B) are included for dichotomous predictors. To interpret the strength of the standardized coefficients of direct effects Cohen's guidelines for the effect size r were used (Cohen, 1988).

Due to sample size limitations, the number of covariates included in each model was restricted. Baseline measurements' correlations with the outcome variables were inspected to identify relevant covariates. Family's global risk (i.e., family's level of psychosocial risk) and child's first language German emerged as meaningful covariates. Both are correlated with several outcome variables (see Table S1 in the Supplementary Materials). They capture important characteristics of the study design, such as differences in German language proficiency among participants and a wide range in family's stress level. Child's gender was included as an additional covariate, because empirical studies show that early achievement and behavior differ by gender, and early childhood education may affect boys and girls differently (Magnuson et al., 2016).

Results

Descriptive statistics

Table 3 shows the manifest mean scores, standard deviation, and range of each variable by treatment group. The bivariate correlations between the variables are displayed in Table S1 (Supplementary Materials).

Longitudinal confirmatory factor analyses

Separate longitudinal CFA models were built for each variable measuring *school adjustment* (i.e., academic achievement, socio-emotional skills, school well-being). Error covariances were allowed in all models for two indicators of the factor socio-emotional skills over time (t3, t5), which was measured at both timepoints by the same scales (post-adaption). The fit indices for each CFA are displayed in Table 4. These models were used as basis to test all the hypotheses.

Direct intervention effects

Fig. S2 (Supplementary Materials) illustrates the pathways for Model 1a. At t3, the intervention showed a significantly positive effect on cognitive ($B = 2.74$, $\beta = 0.13$, $SE = 0.07$, $p = .026$) and socio-emotional

Fig. 1. Illustration of Tested Pathways for Each Outcome of School Adjustment (Model 1–3).

Note. Models 1–3 differed in the outcome variable of school adjustment: a = academic achievement, b = socio-emotional adjustment, c = school well-being. Models 1a–1c tested direct effects (dashed lines). Models 2a–2c tested longitudinal pathways without the treatment group (solid lines). Models 3a–3c included the treatment group and tested the indirect pathways (dotted lines).

Table 3
Descriptive Statistics for Child Outcomes and Child and Family Covariates.

	Control Group						Intervention Group					
	N	M	SD	min	max	SE	N	M	SD	min	max	SE
Cognitive skills t3 ^a	103	90.51	11.08	56.3	120.0	1.09	110	93.21	11.60	60.3	122.0	1.11
Socio-emotional skills t3 ^b	96	55.93	5.94	50.0	72.8	0.61	96	54.29	4.48	50.0	74.3	0.46
Cognitive skills t6 ^c	87	-0.13	0.77	-1.7	1.5	0.08	84	0.12	0.9	-1.9	1.9	1.26
Socio-emotional skills t6 ^b	87	55.71	5.23	50.0	71.3	0.56	79	55.00	5.51	50.0	70.8	0.62
Academic achievement t7 ^d	82	44.55	9.34	18.0	63.0	1.03	83	46.22	8.81	23.5	68.0	0.97
Socio-emotional skills t7 ^e	56	7.66	1.50	4.0	10.0	0.20	70	7.48	1.41	3.7	9.8	0.17
School well-being t7 ^f	71	1.39	0.46	0.1	2.0	0.05	70	1.32	0.45	0.3	2.0	0.05
Covariates Baseline												
Family risk	122	44.85	15.56	10.0	80.0	1.41	139	47.72	16.42	10.0	90.0	1.39
Female (=1)	122	0.20	0.40	0.0	1.0	0.04	139	0.24	0.43	0.0	1.0	0.04
First language German (=1)	122	0.48	0.50	0.0	1.0	0.05	139	0.57	0.50	0.0	1.0	0.04

Note. ^aBSID III (Reuner & Rosenkranz, 2014), IQ scores; CBCL 1½–5 (Achenbach & Rescorla, 2000), T-score; ^cWILMA (Kuratlí Geeler, 2019) and Sprachgewandt (Bayer et al., 2013), z-score; ^dWLLP-R (Schneider et al., 2011) and MBK-1+ (Ennenmoser et al., 2017), T-score; ^eSDQ-Deu (Klasen et al., 2003), sum score; ^fPIQ (Venetz et al., 2015).

skills ($B = 1.75, \beta = 0.18, SE = 0.03, p = .018$). At kindergarten age t6, children in the IG showed higher cognitive skills ($\beta_{IV} = 0.29, \beta = 0.14, SE = 0.08, p = .04$) than children in the CG. There was no significant difference between the two condition groups in terms of socio-emotional skills ($B = 0.83, \beta = 0.09, SE = 0.09, p = .168$). After the transition to primary school no significant direct intervention effects were present on academic achievement ($B = 1.71, \beta = 0.12, SE = 0.10, p = .115$), socio-emotional skills ($B = -0.09, \beta = -0.04, SE = 0.11, p = .625$), and school well-being ($B = -0.06, \beta = -0.08, SE = 0.10, p = .786$).

Female gender had a positive effect only on cognitive skills at t3 ($B = 3.60, \beta = 0.18, p = .013$). German as a first language had a positive effect on cognitive skills at t3 ($B = 4.79, \beta = 0.19, p = .010$), and t6 ($\beta_{IV} = 0.74, \beta = 0.31, p < .001$), as well as on academic achievement at t7 ($B = 3.06, \beta = 0.18, p = .049$). Family’s psychosocial risk had a negative effect on cognitive skills at t3 ($\beta = -0.42, p < .001$) and at t6 ($\beta = -0.31, p < .001$), on socio-emotional skills at t5 ($\beta = -0.17, p = .044$), on academic achievement at t7 ($\beta = -0.30, p = .001$), and on school well-being at t7 ($\beta = -0.24, p = .010$).

Longitudinal SEM with and without indirect intervention effects

The model fits of the longitudinal SEMs with direct effects (models 2a–2c) and the longitudinal SEM with indirect effects (models 3a–3c) are displayed in Table 4. The results are illustrated in Fig. S3a–c (Supplementary Materials).

² Different metrics are used for cognitive skills at t6. Therefore, instead of the unstandardized coefficient B , the coefficients that only standardize the latent variable (β_{IV}) are reported.

Cognitive skills pathway. Children’s early cognitive skills at t3 significantly predicted cognitive skills in kindergarten at t6 ($\beta = 0.57, SE = 0.08, p < .001$), which in turn had a significant positive effect on academic achievement ($\beta = 0.82, SE = 0.09, p < .001$), school well-being ($\beta = 0.70, SE = 0.15, p < .001$), and socio-emotional skills at t7 ($\beta = 0.29, SE = 0.13, p = .016$).

Socio-emotional skills pathway. Children’s socio-emotional skills at t3 significantly predicted their socio-emotional skills in kindergarten at t5 ($\beta = 0.57, SE = 0.09, p < .001$), which in turn predicted socio-emotional skills in primary school at t7 ($\beta = 0.32, SE = 0.12, p = .012$). Socio-emotional skills in kindergarten had no significant effect on academic achievement ($\beta = 0.07, SE = 0.10, p = .234$) and school well-being at t7 ($\beta = -0.11, SE = 0.11, p = .836$). There was no additional significant cross-pathway.

The latent cross-sectional correlation between cognitive and socio-emotional skills was significant at age 3 ($r = 0.22, p = .033$). All covariates affected cognitive skills at t3: Female gender ($B = 3.77, \beta = 0.18, p = .011$) and having German as a first language had positive effects ($B = 5.32, \beta = 0.22, p = .004$), while family stress had a negative effect ($\beta = -0.40, p < .001$). Controlling for cognitive and socio-emotional skills at age 3, the effects of covariates reduced at later time points. German as a first language continued having a positive effect on cognitive skills at t6 ($\beta_{IV} = 0.48, \beta = 0.20, p = .003$) but yielded no significant effect on academic achievement at t7. After t3, family’s psychosocial risk had a negative effect on socio-emotional skills at t5 ($\beta = -0.15, p = .045$).

To investigate the paths of effects of the home-visiting program, longitudinal SEMs with indirect effects (models 3a–3c) were used. The indirect effects from treatment group via cognitive skills at t3 and t6 on academic achievement and school well-being at t7 were significant, indicating a significant cognitive skills pathway for these outcome

Table 4
Confirmatory Factor Analyses and Structural Equation Model Fit Indices.

Model	χ^2	Df	CFI	RMSEA	90% CI
Longitudinal CFA					
Academic achievement	85.08*	65	0.98	0.04	[0.00, 0.06]
Socio-emotional skills	151.33***	92	0.94	0.06	[0.04, 0.07]
School well-being	132.24***	78	0.95	0.06	[0.04, 0.07]
Longitudinal SEM with direct intervention effects					
1a Academic achievement	166.01***	101	0.94	0.05	[0.04, 0.06]
1b Socio-emotional skills	255.10***	136	0.90	0.06	[0.05, 0.07]
1c School well-being	224.79***	118	0.91	0.06	[0.05, 0.07]
Longitudinal SEM without indirect intervention effects					
2a Academic achievement	155.95***	95	0.94	0.05	[0.04, 0.06]
2b Socio-emotional skills	247.81***	128	0.90	0.06	[0.05, 0.07]
2c School well-being	213.59***	111	0.91	0.06	[0.05, 0.07]
Longitudinal SEM with indirect intervention effects					
3a Academic achievement	161.48***	107	0.95	0.05	[0.03, 0.06]
3b Socio-emotional skills	255.53***	142	0.90	0.06	[0.05, 0.07]
3c School well-being	225.38***	124	0.91	0.06	[0.04, 0.07]

Note. CFI = Comparative Fit Index; RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; CI = Confidence Interval. Models 1–3 differ by model specification; a–c indicate outcome domains. Models 1a–1c test direct effects, Models 2a–2c estimate longitudinal pathways without intervention effects, and Models 3a–3c include intervention and test indirect effects. All models met acceptable fit criteria. *** $p < .001$.

variables (see Table 5). The pathway from treatment group via socio-emotional skills at t3 and t6 on socio-emotional skills at t7 was marginally significant. Effect sizes were small and ranged from 0.02 to 0.07.

Discussion

The transition to primary school is a pivotal moment in child development, shaping their educational path and future scholarly success. This transition often poses challenges, particularly for children from at-risk families, as confirmed here by the long-lasting negative

Table 5
Indirect Intervention Effects on School Adjustment.

	B (SE)	β (SE)	p	95% CI ^a
Cognitive pathway				
CS t3 → CS t6 → academic achievement t7	0.94* (0.51)	0.07* (0.04)	.034	[0.258; ∞]
CS t3 → SES t6 → socio-emotional skills t7	0.06+ (0.04)	0.02+ (0.02)	.081	[0.011; ∞]
CS t3 → CS t6 → school well-being t7	0.04* (0.02)	0.06* (0.03)	.032	[0.012; ∞]
Socio-emotional pathway				
SES t3 → SES t5 → academic achievement t7	0.10 (0.15)	0.01 (0.01)	.263	[-0.074; ∞]
SES t3 → SES t5 → socio-emotional skills t7	0.08+ (0.05)	0.03+ (0.02)	.084	[0.019; ∞]
SES t3 → SES t5 → school well-being t7	-0.01 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	.807	[-0.036; ∞]

Note. CI = confidence interval; CS = cognitive skills; SES = socio-emotional skills. CS t3 → t6 denotes the cognitive pathway, and SES t3 → SES t5 denotes the socio-emotional pathway. ^a One-sided CI for unstandardized coefficients (B). *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$, + $p < .10$.

effect of psychosocial stress on numerous outcomes after school entry. The main purpose of this study was to examine whether the home visiting program PAT supports this transition via cognitive and socio-emotional pathways.

PAT participation was associated with early improvements in cognitive and socio-emotional skills at age 3, consistent with previous results (Schaub et al., 2019). However, while the cognitive advantage persisted into kindergarten, effects on socio-emotional skills became weaker. Notably, no significant direct effects were found on socio-emotional skills in kindergarten, or on academic achievement, socio-emotional skills, and school well-being at Grade 1. Thus, hypothesis 1 was not supported.

Concerning hypothesis 2, early cognitive skills predicted academic achievement, socio-emotional skills, and school well-being, whereas socio-emotional skills predicted only socio-emotional adjustment. Finally, mediation (Hypothesis 3) was partially supported. PAT contributed indirectly to school adjustment primarily through cognitive, rather than socio-emotional pathways.

Effects of the home visiting program PAT

The absence of direct effects contrasts findings from some intense, often nurse-led home visiting programs, as well as from a small number of earlier evaluations of PAT and other parent-focused interventions (e.g., Doyle & the Preparing for Life Evaluation Team, 2019; Kitzman et al., 2010; Lahti et al., 2019; Pais & Sexer, 2023; Price et al., 2023; Robling et al., 2021). Several factors may explain this. First, many of the studies reporting stronger effects were based on larger samples or intervention models with higher intensity and professional specialization (e.g., nurse-led delivery), which increases statistical power and may enhance program impact. In addition, some earlier evaluations of PAT were not randomized controlled trials, potentially inflating effect estimates.

Second, differences in participant characteristics are likely relevant. Evidence from the home visiting literature suggests that the largest and most sustained effects are observed among families facing very high psychosocial risk (Kitzman et al., 2010; Schaub et al., 2019). In contrast to highly targeted programs such as NFP, which focuses on very young, first-time mothers in severely disadvantaged circumstances (Kitzman et al., 2010), mothers in the present study were older on average and only about half were first-time parents, potentially limiting the scope for detectable intervention effects.

Third, contextual factors related to the broader service environment may have attenuated group differences. Families in the control group had access to a relatively well-developed system of universal health and social services (Schoch et al. 2020), which may reduce contrasts between intervention and control condition by narrowing differences in service exposure outside the program. This context differs from settings with more selective or means-tested service provision, as in the U.S., where access barriers might be higher and home visiting programs may play a more distinctive role (Palermo et al., 2024).

Finally, program duration and continuity may be important (Reynolds et al., 2010). PAT ended at age 3, resulting in a gap before kindergarten entry. Programs that extend support closer to school entry may be better positioned to directly influence school adjustment (Doyle & the Preparing for Life Evaluation Team, 2019).

Pathways of effects: cognitive and socio-emotional skills

Improved cognitive skills persisted through kindergarten and contributed to better academic achievement, school well-being, and, to a lesser extent, socio-emotional skills in Grade 1. These findings align with research showing that gains in cognitive outcomes can endure and are key predictors of later success (Campbell et al., 1998; Duncan et al., 2007; Reynolds & Ou, 2011; Schweinhart et al., 1993). The results also suggest that stronger early cognitive skills may indirectly support socio-emotional development and school well-being, in line with

findings linking cognitive abilities to social and emotional functioning (Wikman et al., 2022), and higher academic skills to greater school well-being (Grüter et al., 2023; Kytälä et al., 2025).

Thus, home visiting may foster a cognitive advantage that not only supports academic achievement but also facilitates a smoother transition to school by promoting socio-emotional adjustment and enhancing school well-being.

PAT improved socio-emotional outcomes at the end of the program, and this advantage partially persisted into the first year of formal schooling. Nevertheless, these sustained socio-emotional gains did not contribute to improvements in academic achievement or overall school well-being in Grade 1. These findings are consistent with longitudinal studies showing that socio-emotional gains do not always translate into later academic attainment (Ou, 2005; Reynolds & Ou, 2011). However, it is noteworthy that socio-emotional gains did not predict school well-being, despite well-established associations between socio-emotional skills and children's emotional, social, and academic inclusion in school (Grüter et al., 2023).

One explanation may be that socio-emotional skills acquired in the home do not automatically generalize to school settings, which involve new expectations, peer networks, and teacher relationships (Rimm-Kaufmann & Pianta, 2000). This interpretation is also consistent with the nature of the measurement approach, given that socio-emotional skills at earlier time points were assessed exclusively via parent-report measures, which primarily capture children's behavior and regulation within the home context. School well-being is shaped strongly by the child's experience within the classroom microsystem, including teacher support, peer acceptance, and classroom climate (Grüter et al., 2023; Hoferichter et al., 2021; Rucinski et al., 2018), and children may need additional opportunities to practice socio-emotional skills in group settings for these to impact school well-being.

Home visiting to help transition to primary school

This study focused on developmental pathways that support children's successful transition to primary school. Home visiting programs are designed to strengthen parenting skills and practices and promote school readiness (Lahti et al., 2019) by fostering cognitively and emotionally responsive caregiving (King et al., 2019). Parents in at-risk families may have limited capacity to provide such stimulation, and PAT aims to enrich the home environment accordingly. Given the stronger observed impact on children's cognitive development, it is likely that the intervention was more effective in promoting cognitive stimulation than emotional support.

School adjustment, however, emerges from interactions between family, school, and the broader community (Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 2006; Rimm-Kaufman & Pianta, 2000). Although PAT strengthened early cognitive and some socio-emotional foundations, teacher and peer relationships during the school transition become increasingly influential. For example, a strong teacher-student relationship can compensate for lower child self-regulation and increase academic achievement (Liew et al., 2010). These new relationships, both teacher-student and peer-peer, can on the one hand reinforce previously gained advantages, but on the other hand may also increase stress for some children and thereby offset earlier gains. Therefore, these findings suggest that early home visiting may need to be complemented by transition-supportive school practices to translate early gains into sustained school adjustment, particularly for children from at-risk backgrounds.

Study strengths and limitations

A major strength of this study is the combination of an experimental design with a long-term longitudinal follow-up, which remains rare in evaluations of home visiting programs with at-risk samples. In addition, the intervention was implemented under real-world conditions rather than in a laboratory setting, enhancing ecological validity and practical

relevance. This study also contributes to the limited body of evidence on the effectiveness of U.S.-based home visiting programs in non-English-speaking countries, thus demonstrating the practical applicability and potential usefulness of the PAT program in non-English speaking contexts. The effort that was made to lower barriers and gain trust of the families through translated documents, cultural interpreters and other measures might have played an important role in this success.

Several limitations must also be acknowledged. Although a substantial proportion of families remained in the study through Grade 1, longitudinal attrition resulted in a reduced sample size at t7, which limited statistical power and constrained the detection of small effects. Accordingly, findings, particularly null results, should be interpreted with caution. Also, socio-emotional adjustment was assessed solely via parent's report, which may predominantly reflect behavior in the home environment and may partly explain the missing effect on school well-being. Second, different instruments were used across time points, precluding formal tests of longitudinal measurement invariance. As a field-based study, data collection was subject to greater variability in assessment conditions. In addition, several parent-report measures (e.g., CBCL, SDQ) were administered in translated but not formally validated versions for non-German-speaking families, which may have introduced additional measurement error. Together with model complexity and the relatively small sample size, these factors may have reduced statistical power and affected model fit. Third, the relatively low proportion of families with very high psychosocial risk restricts generalizability, although these families are the ones who benefit most from home visiting (Jungmann et al., 2015; Schaub et al., 2019). Consequently, the program might be even more effective within this group than the findings suggest. Further, the sample was recruited from the urban metropolitan area of Zurich. The potential impact of PAT in rural areas could not be evaluated. The coverage of services in rural areas tend to be lower than in urban areas (von Rhein et al. 2025), suggesting that the impact of intervention might potentially be larger in rural areas, which is to be evaluated in future studies. Finally, most families spoke a language other than German. Although language background was controlled for in all analyses, the study did not examine how early PAT-supported parent-child interaction relates specifically to later acquisition of the school language. As PAT encourages parents to use their strongest language, effects on German-language development are likely indirect and shaped later through preschool and school-based support.

Future directions

The home and school learning environments after the program ends have a significant impact on the long-term outcomes of early education (Reynolds et al., 2010). Future research needs to examine how changes in parenting practices induced by home visiting interact with school contexts, including teachers' instructional practices and school environments. As children progress through school, motivational and peer-related processes become increasingly important (Ou, 2005).

Prior intervention research suggests several developmental trajectories (Ansari, 2018), including persistence (Reynolds & Ou, 2011), convergence (Bailey et al., 2017), and sleeper effects (Jeong et al., 2021). Continued follow-up beyond early primary school is therefore essential to determine the longer-term trajectory of the cognitive and socio-emotional pathways identified here.

Future research should also investigate which specific components of home visiting drive lasting change to refine program delivery. By identifying which components matter most, practices such as shared book reading, guided play, or emotion-sensitive caregiving may differently support cognitive versus socio-emotional pathways. The inclusion of observational measures of socio-emotional functioning in school would also allow stronger conclusions about contextual transfer. Finally, research should examine how home visiting can be systematically linked to school-based transition practices to promote continuity of support during this critical period.

Conclusion

The transition from kindergarten to primary school is a developmental milestone that draws on skills shaped long before school entry. While no direct effects of PAT on school adjustment in Grade 1 were found, the longitudinal analyses show that PAT supported children's school adjustment indirectly, primarily by fostering early cognitive development. Socio-emotional skills also improved at the end of the intervention, though their effects on later outcomes were more limited. Overall, the findings suggest that home visiting programs delivered in the first three years of life can contribute to children's successful transition to primary school by strengthening early foundational skills.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Isabelle Kalkusch: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Simone Schaub:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Carmen L.A. Zurbriggen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Alex Neuhauser:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Patsawee Rodcharoen:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Minna Törmänen:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Andrea Lanfranchi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Peter Klaver:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

None.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.ecresq.2026.05.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2026.05.001).

Data availability

After data curation for each project period, the data is published on SWISSUbase (w www.swissubase.ch). Data for t0-t3 (Ref. 13906) and t5-t6 (Ref. 10470) are already available.

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